

Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Cobalt

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Spectrophotometric method for the determination of cobalt is given. The basis of the method is to convert cobalt into the stable and less sensitive to light tris(malonato)cobaltate(III) anion. Iron, nickel and chromium may be present in a reasonable amount. The accuracy of the method is better than 2% of the quantity estimated.

COBALT reacts with so many ligands with the formation of coloured cobalt complexes. These coloured cobalt complexes have been used extensively for the detection and estimation of cobalt. Among these are the Carbonate CO_3^{2-} and Oxalate $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$. Telep and Boltz¹ have shown that the triscarbonatocobalt(III) has an absorbancy maximum in ultraviolet region at 260 $m\mu$. The green colour of triscarbonatocobaltate(III) complex is specific for cobalt and has been used as basis for colorimetric method for cobalt determination^{2,3}. The same complex was also utilized as a basis for titrimetric method for analysis of cobalt complexes^{4,5}. An iodometric method for the determination of cobalt based on the conversion of cobalt to triscarbonatocobaltate(III) complex has been given by Laitinen and Burdett⁶. A polarographic method for the determination of cobalt as trisoxalatocobaltate(III) has been given by Kolthoff and Watters⁷. The green trisoxalatocobaltate(III) has a maximum absorption at 605 $m\mu$, and spectrophotometric method for cobalt determination based on this complex was given by Cartledge and Nichols⁸. Reaction between Malonate $\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and Cr(III) has been used as photometric method for determination of chromium⁹.

Herein a spectrophotometric method for cobalt determination based upon the formation of green tris(malonato)cobaltate(III) complex¹⁰ is described. This complex has two absorption maxima at 425 $m\mu$ and 615 $m\mu$ with maximum extinction coefficients of 114 and 128 respectively. The method is based upon oxidizing cobaltous ion in weakly acidic solution of potassium malonate according to the reaction

Experimental

Unicam SP. 500 series 2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm, silica cells was used for the absorbancy measurements.

Standard cobalt solution was made by dissolving cobaltous chloride (A.R. Grade) in redistilled water and its cobalt content was determined by three successive electrolytic method. Potassium malonate solution was made from the neutralization of potassium hydroxide with malonic acid. Other solutions were prepared by dissolving their salts in water to get the required concentration.

Maximum Extinction Coefficient :

The maximum extinction coefficients of the cobalt(III) complex malonate at 425 $m\mu$ and 615 $m\mu$ were estimated. Solutions of reprecipitated potassium tris(malonato)cobaltate(III) were made and the absorbance was recorded. 1.0728 g (0.002 mol) of $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{mal})_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken and dissolved and made up to 100 ml in a volumetric flask. This gave 0.02M solution. Another four solutions were made from 0.02M solution by dilution. All were made to 100 ml in volumetric flasks and the optical densities were measured at 425 $m\mu$ and 615 $m\mu$. The slope of the curve obtained from plotting optical density against concentration gave the maximum extinction coefficient. Any small amount of cobaltous malonate resulting from slight decomposition of the complex has negligible effect since its extinction coefficient is 2.7.

The molar concentration of tris(malonato)cobaltate anion could be calculated as follows :

$$C = \frac{d}{E \cdot l}$$

in which d is the measured density ($\log \frac{I_0}{I}$), E is maximum extinction coefficient at defined wave

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF MAXIMUM EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT

Wave length in $m\mu$	Molar Conc. of $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{mal})_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Density
615	0.002	0.274
615	0.004	0.538
615	0.006	0.770
615	0.008	1.020
615	0.020	—

Maximum Extinction Coefficient is 128.4.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF MAXIMUM EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT

Wave length in $m\mu$	Molar Conc. of $K_2[Co(mal)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$	Density
425	0.002	0.242
425	0.004	0.475
425	0.006	0.680
425	0.008	0.918
425	0.020	—

Maximum Extinction Coefficient is 114.

length and l is the cell length in cm. The cobalt content of the sample in mg can be estimated from the molar concentration C . If the oxidised solution was diluted to 100 ml before absorption measurements and assuming one cm cell was used, the weight of cobalt was determined from the relation :

$$\text{mg Co} = 45.9 d$$

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt :

A neutralized sample containing between 1 and 20 mg of cobalt in a volumetric flask was taken and 2 ml of glacial acetic acid, 5 ml of 20% ammonium acetate, 10 ml of 0.5M potassium malonate and 1 g of lead dioxide were added. The sample was kept for 10 to 20 minutes and shaken at every five minutes. The solution was then diluted without filtration to the mark. The flask was shaken twice and allowed to settle for few minutes and the solution was then filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The first batch of the filtrate should not be taken ; the second batch was taken directly into the absorption cell and the optical density was measured.

Results

Interfering Elements :

Chromium(III), iron(III), nickel, copper and manganese interfere. Chromium(III) interferes but can be converted into weakly absorbing dichromate by preliminary oxidation. Iron(III) and nickel have a weak absorption at 615 $m\mu$ Tables (5a, 5b and 5c). Copper and manganese should be removed before oxidation of cobalt. The effects of the interfering elements were shown in terms of mg of cobalt.

Even when comparatively large amount of the interfering elements are present only small fraction in mg is going to be added to the cobalt analysis result. Cobalt determination in the absence and presence of these interfering elements are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF COBALT

mg Co taken	Volume of Sol	Density	mg Co obt.	mg Error
1.91	100	0.042	1.91	+0.00
3.82	100	0.082	3.75	-0.07
5.73	100	0.123	5.66	-0.07
9.55	100	0.212	9.74	+0.19
11.66	100	0.258	11.86	+0.20
13.37	100	0.294	13.52	+0.15
15.28	100	0.330	15.19	-0.09
17.19	100	0.375	17.23	+0.04
19.10	100	0.418	19.23	+0.13

TABLE 5a—INTERFERING ELEMENTS

mg of Ni	Volume of solution ml	Density	mg Co. represented
10	100	0.005	0.22
20	"	0.007	0.32
30	"	0.008	0.36
40	"	0.009	0.41
50	"	0.010	0.45
60	"	0.011	0.50
70	"	0.130	0.59

TABLE 5b

mg of Fe	Volume of solution ml	Density	mg Co. represented
10	100	0.001	0.04
20	"	0.003	0.13
30	"	0.004	0.18
40	"	0.004	0.18
50	"	0.005	0.22
60	"	0.006	0.27
70	"	0.007	0.32

TABLE 5c

mg of Chromium as $K_2Cr_2O_7$	Volume of solution ml	Density	mg Co. represented
10	100	0.004	0.18
20	"	0.005	0.22
30	"	0.006	0.27
40	"	0.007	0.32
50	"	0.008	0.36
60	"	0.009	0.41
70	"	0.010	0.45

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF COBALT IN THE PRESENCE OF INTERFERING ELEMENTS

mg of Co taken	mg of Ni added	mg of Cr as $K_2Cr_2O_7$ added	mg of Fe added	Volume of solution ml	Density	mg of Co obt	mg Error
8.55	9.6	5.17	36.18	100	0.193	8.86	+0.31
11.40	11.2	6.03	42.21	"	0.249	11.44	+0.04
14.20	12.8	6.89	48.24	"	0.317	14.57	+0.37
17.10	14.4	7.76	54.27	"	0.378	17.98	+0.28
19.95	16.0	8.62	60.30	"	0.439	20.18	+0.23
22.80	17.6	9.48	66.33	"	0.494	22.68	+0.12

AL-OBADIE : SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF COBALT

Comparison among carbonato, oxalato and malonato cobalt(III) complexes as methods for cobalt determination, carbonato complex is not stable and an excess of oxidising agent is required to maintain cobalt in the complex forms. The u.v. spectrum of the carbonatocobalt(III) complex is more sensitive than the visible spectrum¹. On the other hand, the oxalato cobalt(III) complex is sensitive to light. Thus using the oxalato method the complex should not be exposed to bright light. The advantage of the malonato method lies in the fact that the trismalonatocobaltate(III) anion is stable in solution and not sensitive to light.

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